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Islamic Astronomy in Sanskrit

DAVID PINGREE*

The problem that I wish to examine in this paper involves in particular the awareness of and reaction to Islamic astronomy on the part of the traditional Indian astronomers practicing their science in northern India under the Moghuls. But in more general terms I believe that it illustrates the characteristic methods by which Indians throughout their history, until the nineteenth century, have responded to a superior foreign science (the judgment of superiority is here based on experience rather than on theory), though in the last phases of Moghul astronomy in Sanskrit one can perceive the beginnings of a new attitude foreshadowing that which has become the prevalent one among contemporary Indian scientists. Briefly, the shift in attitudes to which I allude is from the classical position that alien scientific systems may be adopted to Indian use, but that they must somehow be made to conform to the older Sanskrit tradition, and the resulting mutation ought to be presented as the revelation of a divinity or of an *ṛṣi*; the attitude of the contemporary Indian scientist is, normally, that there is one scientific method, internationally approved of and validated by experience and by its pragmatic success, and that the views expressed by gods and seers in the past are not guides to scientific truth, though some weaker souls may wish to vindicate them by reinterpreting them to conform to, and thus to anticipate, contemporary scientific hypotheses.

In the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries Indian intellectuals were forced to respond to a forerunner of modern science in the form of Ptolemaic astronomy as practiced by Muslims.¹ Though accepting Aristotelian physics, Muslim astronomers for a variety of reasons, not the least of which was the availability of the conflicting Ptolemaic and Indian models and parameters

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1. For biographical and bibliographical information on the authors discussed in these pages I refer the reader to D. Pingree, *Census of the Exact Sciences in Sanskrit* (henceforth *CESS*), of which Series A, vols. 1-3 have appeared as *Memoirs of the American Philosophical Society*, vols. 81, 86, and 111 (vol. 4 is in press), and to C. A. Storey, *Persian Literature*, vol. 2, part 1 (henceforth *Storey*), (London, 1958). See also D. Pingree, "Essay on the History of Indian Astronomy" (henceforth *Essay*, cited according to formulas and tables) in *Dictionary of Scientific Biography*, vol. 15, (New York, 1978), where the few technical matters touched on in this paper are discussed, and B. Datta, "Introduction of Arabic and Persian Mathematics into Sanskrit Literature", *PBMS* 14 (1932), 7-21.

of planetary motion to scientists of the early 'Abbasid period,² emphasized – perhaps over-emphasized – the role of observation in refining planetary theories, and because of this emphasis developed both the necessary instruments and theories of optics and of the behavior of light. The most noteworthy Indian reaction to these aspects of Islamic astronomy, though characteristically having no discernible practical effect, was the program for the reform of Indian astronomy instituted by Jayasīṃha, the Mahārāja of Amber from 1700 till 1743.³ Under his patronage were built the massive observatories at Vārāṇasī, Ujjayinī, Mathurā, Dillī, and his own Jayapura, while under his patronage the industrious Jagannātha⁴ translated Euclid's *Elements* and Ptolemy's *Almagest* into Sanskrit, and the less well-known Nayanasukhopādhyāya,⁵ at the dictation in Persian of Muḥammad Ābida (who acted as an intermediary in the way that Spanish-speaking Jews had for some of the Latin translators of Spain in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries) translated Theodosius' *Spherics* and Naṣīr al-Dīn's *Tadhkira* with al-Barjandi's *Sharḥ* thereon. But these achievements, impressive though they might appear, were at the end rather than the beginning of the Islamic influence on Indian astronomy. Let us turn now to the predecessors of that beginning.

Non-Ptolemaic forms of Greek astronomy, sharing many characteristics with what we can reasonably reconstruct of the theories of Hipparchus, were transmitted to India in the third or fourth century A.D., including several alternative planetary models and mathematical descriptions of other celestial phenomena;⁶ these were given their characteristic Indian expressions in the fifth, sixth, and seventh centuries, from which developed four of the five schools of astronomy or pakṣas – in chronological order the Brāhma, the Ārya, the Ārdharātrika, and the Saura. These astronomical schools were generally conservative, but did permit the development of new computational techniques; and it is in the mathematics ancillary to astronomy – trigonometry and indeterminate equations – rather than in astronomy itself that the Indians excelled. There was no tradition of systematic observation in early Indian astronomy.

The Hellenistic lunar model that was transmitted to India allowed for only one inequality in its motion, which was accounted for by an epicycle; Ptolemy's model had a more complex structure, with the center of the moon's deferent traveling on a concentric at double the rate of the mean elongation

2. D. Pingree, "The Greek Influence on Early Islamic Mathematical Astronomy", *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 93 (1973), 32-43.

3. CESS A3, 63a-64b, and A4.

4. CESS A3, 56a-58a, and A4.

5. CESS A3, 132a, and A4.

6. D. Pingree, "The Recovery of Early Greek Astronomy from India", *Journal for the History of Astronomy*, 7 (1976), 109-123.

between the sun and the moon. The result of Ptolemy's model, with its specified dimensions, is that the maximum equation at syzygies is $5;1^0$, at quadratures $7;40^0$. In the tenth century a model producing an identical effect first appears in India. The epoch of Muñjāla's⁷ lost *Bṛhanmānasa* is 9 March 932 at noon (noon-epoch in itself is characteristic of Ptolemaic and Islamic astronomy, but alien to India); his extant *Laghumānasa* was commented on by Praśastadhara⁸ in Kāśmīra in 958; and both of these treatises were encountered by al-Bīrūnī in the Pañjāb in the 1020's. It is likely, therefore, that, although Muñjāla's *Laghumānasa* is now found only in South India, he originally composed it in the West or Northwest, and had contact there directly or indirectly, with Muslim astronomers.

Muñjāla, however, following the Indian tradition, did not regard planetary models as cinematic or as in any way representing physical reality, but as calculating devices. Thus he felt free to replace Ptolemy's crank mechanism with an elegant formulation of the evection.⁹

$$0 = (\bar{v}_m - 11^0) \cdot \text{Cos}(\lambda_s - \lambda_a) \cdot \text{Sin}(\lambda_m - \lambda_s),$$

where λ denotes celestial longitude, and the subscripts m , s , and a denote moon, sun, and apogee respectively. Because of his choice to express his parameters as integer parts of a radius of 488, his simple lunar model generates a maximum equation of $5;2^0$; while his formula for evection, since he employs the integer 11^0 in the first factor, results in a maximum of about $2;29^0$, so that Muñjāla's maximum lunar equation at quadratures is $7;31^0$ instead of Ptolemy's $7;40^0$.

A result closer to Ptolemy's was provided by Srīpati,¹⁰ who wrote various works between 1039 and 1056, at Rohiṅkhaṇḍa, about 150 miles south of Ujjayinī. Srīpati accepts the Brāhmapakṣa's simple lunar model with an epicycle that pulsates in a complex fashion as the body approaches the horizon, but which at its mean, in the meridian, produces a maximum equation of $5;2,7^0$. For the evection Srīpati¹¹ accepts Muñjāla's formulation, but modifies the first term so that the maximum correction is $2;40^0$ —just 1 minute more than Ptolemy's—and the maximum equation at quadratures, when the center of the moon's epicycle is on the meridian, is $7;42,7^0$.

Srīpati also gives a complete formulation of the equation of time including both that part which is due to the sun's velocity, which had already been known to Brahmagupta,¹² and that dependent on the sun's longitude. It

7. CESS A1.

8. CESS A4.

9. *Laghumānasa* 18-19; *Essay* IX 1.

10. CESS A6.

11. *Siddhāntaśekhara* 11, 2-4; *Essay* v 123.

12. CESS A4. *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta* 2, 29; *Essay* V 66.

is probable that he derived this second component also from an Islamic source. It was also known to his contemporary, Bhojarāja,¹³ who wrote the *Rājamrgāṅka*, with epoch of 21 February 1042, at Dhārā in Mālava.

It is highly unlikely, however, that this source should have been the translations of Euclid's *Elements* and of Ptolemy's *Almagest* that al-Bīrūnī claimed, in about 1030, to be engaged in.¹⁴ This claim must be regarded as sheer bravado, since the knowledge of astronomers' Sanskrit displayed by al-Bīrūnī and his paṇḍitas was totally inadequate to the task. Another channel of scholarly exchange must be imagined, and of a more limited character; the only elements of Islamic astronomy that appear in Sanskrit texts at this early date relate to the sun and the moon.

The next phase in the transmission of Islamic astronomy to India, if we regard Bhāskara's¹⁵ innovations in trigonometry as entirely his own, was the introduction of the astrolabe into Western India under the Tughluqs. Mahendra Sūri¹⁶ composed the first description of this instrument in Sanskrit, the *Yantrarāja*, at Bṛh̥gupura – that is, modern Broach in Gujarat – in about 1370; according to his pupil, Malayendu,¹⁷ who wrote a commentary on the *Yantrarāja* in about 1382, Mahendra undertook to write his treatise at the request of the astronomers of Fīrūz Shāh (1351-1388), during whose reign Sanskrit works were also translated into Persian. The astrolabe itself, of course, was developed in the Roman empire, though our earliest extant examples are Arabic. Mahendra and Malayendu not only introduced the construction and use of the instrument to Indian astronomers, but also an Islamic sine table in which R equals 3600 or 1, 0, 0; a table of declinations with the Islamic value, $23;35^{\circ}$, for the obliquity of the ecliptic; a list of the latitudes of 77 cities, most of which are in India though many are located elsewhere in the Middle East (the Ptolemaic system of representing terrestrial coordinates had not previously been used in Sanskrit texts); a catalogue of 32 astrolabe stars whose coordinates are derived from the *Almagest*, with the Ptolemaic longitudes corrected for precession (at the rate of 1° in $66 \frac{2}{3}$ years) for 1370; and the cotangent tables normal on the backs of Eastern Islamic astrolabes.¹⁸ Thus, in those elements necessary for the use of the astrolabe – trigonometry, terrestrial latitudes, and the coordinates

13. CESS A4. *Rājamrgāṅka* 1, 25; *Essay* V 124.

14. D. Pingree, "Al-Bīrūnī's Knowledge of Sanskrit Astronomical Texts", in *The Scholar and the Saint* (New York, 1975), pp. 67-81.

15. CESS A4. *Siddhāntasīroman* 1, 2, 23; *Essay* Table V 43, and jyotpatti 16 and 21; *Essay* V 127-128.

16. CESS A4.

17. CESS A4.

18. *Yantrarājaṭīkā* 1, 5-6; *Yantrarāja* 1, 22-40, and 1, 70; *Essay* Tables XI 1 - XI 3.

of the astrolabe stars – Mahendra is quite willing to substitute Islamic procedures and values for the Indian, without any apparent effort to determine in what sense they might be superior; it was easier to take them over than to recast them in an Indian mold. In the other elements of astronomy he gives no indication that it is at all advisable to abandon or modify existing Indian theories.

The next major infusion of Islamic astronomy into science in Sanskrit seems to have occurred under the Moghuls, who, like Fīrūz Shāh, promoted intellectual exchanges between their Muslim and Hindu subjects. I employ the word “major” because there is one minor case of transmission that cannot be ignored. The Kerala astronomer, Acyuta Piṣāraṭī,¹⁹ in his *Sphuṭanirṇaya* and *Rāṣigolasphuṭānīti* written in the 1590’s, proposed a formula for reducing the mean longitude of the moon in its orbit to an ecliptic longitude. Such a reduction had first been suggested, by Yaḥyā ibn Abī Maṣṣūr in the *Zij al-mumtaḥan*, composed under al-Maḥmūd in the 820’s. Acyuta probably bears witness to some transmission of at least a part of Islamic lunar theory that took place on the Malabar Coast in the fifteenth or sixteenth century.

A survey of Sanskrit astronomical texts composed in Western and Northern India in the sixteenth century, however, has yielded no reflexions of Islamic astronomy. I have examined, among others, the works, published and unpublished, composed by Jñānarāja²⁰ at Pārthapura on the Godāvārī in 1503; by Gaṇeśa²¹ at Nandigram in Gujarat between 1520 and 1552; by Dinakara²² at Bārejya in Gujarat between 1578 and 1583; by Gaṇeśa’s nephew and pupil, Nṛsimha,²³ at Nandigrāma between 1588 and 1603; and by Rāmacandra²⁴ at Benāres between 1590 and 1600. Members of the families of several of these sixteenth century astronomers, however, were the leading advocates and critics of Islamic astronomy in Benares in the seventeenth century.

But the first author to whom we must refer is Viśrāma from Jambūsara in Gujarat, who wrote a description of various astronomical instruments, the *Yantraśiromaṇi*,²⁵ in 1615. What is of immediate interest to us in his work is the inclusion of the Babylonian Goal-year periods of the planets,²⁶ which, of course, figure prominently in Book IX of Ptolemy’s *Almagest*, and

19. CESS A1, 36b-38b, and A4. *Rāṣigolasphuṭānīti* 47; *Essay* IX 2.

20. CESS A3, 75a-76b.

21. CESS A2, 94a-106b; A3, 27b-28a; and A4.

22. CESS A3, 102b-104b, and A4.

23. CESS A3, 202b-204a.

24. CESS A5.

25. CESS A5.

26. *Yantraśiromaṇi* 92-94.

are repeated often in Islamic zijes. These Goal-year periods, with the exception that Venus' eight-year period was altered to a 227-year period, were soon used as the basis of an enormous set of planetary tables, the *Jagadbhūṣana*, compiled by Haridatta²⁷ in Mewar in Rājasthān in 1638; Haridatta, however, apparently used an Indian rather than a Persian set of astronomical tables in carrying out the computations of his own tables; the same is true of Trivikrama,²⁸ who composed a similar set of planetary tables based on the Goal-year periods at Nalinapura in 1704. Their knowledge of the Goal-year periods, then, simply provided a convenient framework for a form of perpetual tables, as it had in the West for al-Zarqālī and his source and successors.

In Benares in the eighteenth century the most important astronomers belonged to two Mahārāṣṭrian Brāhmaṇa families which had migrated to the city in the sixteenth century. The descendents of Cintāmani, a member of the Devarātragotra residing at Dadhigrāma on the Payoṣṇī, include Munīśvara Viśvarūpa,²⁹ who was born in 1603, the year in which his father, Raṅganātha,³⁰ completed his famous *ṭikā* on the *Sūryasiddhānta*, the *Gūḍhārthaparakāśikā*. Munīśvara's great rival was Kamalākara,³¹ who was descended through Divākara, a pupil of Gaṇeśa, from Rāma of the Bhāradvājagotra, a resident of Golagrāma on the Godāvarī, not more than a few days' journey from Dadhigrāma. These two men and their numerous siblings, cousins, and nephews were all engaged in astronomical activities, but always within the context of the traditional Indian siddhāntas, particularly those of the Saura and Brāhma pakṣas. From time to time, however, they display an awareness of Islamic astronomy, which seems to have been available to them in the form of a Sanskrit translation of the *Zij* completed by Ulugh Beg³² at Samarqand in about 1437/1438 or some derivative of that zij. The precise source of their knowledge remains obscure, however, we will return to the question of the Sanskrit versions of Ulugh Beg's astronomy later in this paper.

The earliest of these Benares astronomers to demonstrate a knowledge of Islamic astronomy is Kamalākara's father, Nṛsimha,³³ who wrote a commentary on the *Sūryasiddhānta* in 1611 and one on the *Siddhāntasiromanī* of Bhāskara in 1621. Unfortunately, of these two gigantic works all that has been published is his commentary on the first adhikāra of the grahagaṇita

27. CESS A6.

28. CESS A3, 92b-93b, and A4.

29. CESS A4.

30. CESS A5.

31. CESS A2, 21a-23a; A3, 18a; and A4.

32. CESS A4; Storey, pp. 67-72.

33. CESS A3, 204a-206a.

section of the *Siddhāntasiromaṇi*.³⁴ In this he criticizes the theory of the Yavanas (i.e., the Muslims) that there is an unmoved crystalline (*kāca*) sphere supporting the sphere of the constellations (*mūrtimat*) and enabling it to rotate daily from East to West; for, he says, the crystal could not bear such a weight, especially since the sphere of the constellations in its turn bears the weight of the sphere of the zodiac. What else he might have derived from a Muslim source I do not know, as I have not had an opportunity to examine manuscripts of his other works.

The same is also true of most of the *Siddhāntasārvabhauma*, which was completed by Munīśvara³⁵ on 7 September 1646; of its twelve adhyāyas, on which Munīśvara wrote his own *ṭīkā*, only the first two and part of the third have been published with their commentary. In these chapters are found such relatively trivial matters as the recording of the definition of a sidereal month according to the Pārasīkas³⁶ (Munīśvara claims that the concept is useful for astral omens, but not in astronomy); it is stated that the origin of longitudes in the geographical tables of the Pārasīkas is a city called Khāladātta near Romaka³⁷ (in fact, of course, this place is the Eternal Islands – *al-jazā'ir al-khālidāt* – of Arabic geographers); it is claimed that, even though the methods of the Pārasīkas for correcting the mean longitudes of the planets beginning with the moon are described in the language of the gods (that is, in Sanskrit), yet they must be rejected by the wise because they are without proof;³⁸ and it is mentioned that, whereas for the orthodox the blue sky is a sphere of metal (a *lohagola*), the Pārasīkas claim that the heavenly spheres are crystalline.³⁹ All of these matters, even the last, seem to trouble Munīśvara very little; the reader is warned against some, but never in a very emphatic manner. He was much more incensed by the theory of precession when understood to imply a tropical rather than a sidereal reference system. For the Indians, though they have various theories of precession and trepidation,⁴⁰ traditionally used them only for the correction of the sun's declination; the juncture of the sun's declination circle with the equator may be permitted to move with respect to the fixed stars, but the traditional Indian method of describing mean motions as integer numbers of sidereal rotations within a *Kalpa* or a *Mahāyuga* necessitated, in Munīśvara's opinion, the unswerving connection of the origin of the zodiac with

34. *Marīci* 1, 2, 1-6.

35. *CESS* A4.

36. *Siddhāntasārvabhauma* 1, 17.

37. *Siddhāntasārvabhaumaṭīkā* 1, 136.

38. *Siddhāntasārvabhauma* 2, 222.

39. *Siddhāntasārvabhauma* 2, 228.

40. D. Pingree, "Precession and Trepidation in Indian Astronomy before A. D. 1200", *Journal for the History of Astronomy*, 3 (1972), 27-35.

a particular fixed star. Thus he severely criticizes the Pārasīkas, their Yavana predecessors, and their Indian followers, for their arrogance in adhering to a doctrine dependent on their own deductions (*svamati*) even though they are contrary to the opinions of the ṛṣis;⁴¹ at one point he even asserts that ridicule arises against anyone who has confidence in the words of the Yavanas on this matter through misunderstanding the true meaning of precession in Indian astronomy and trusting those observations that the Yavanas call *rasada* (Arabic *raṣad*).⁴² Munīśvara's objections to precession were attacked by Kamalākara's brother, Raṅganātha,⁴³ in his *Lohagolakhaṇḍaṇa*, which in turn was assailed by Munīśvara's cousin, Gadādharma,⁴⁴ in a work entitled *Lohagolasamarthana*.

Thus Munīśvara's knowledge of the Sanskrit version of an Islamic astronomical work has not been allowed to influence his astronomical theories in any significant way. At best he refers with indifference to some aspect of Islamic science, but more commonly he feels at least obliged to deny validity to what he does find it necessary to mention. And his ultimate weapon against the observational basis of Ptolemaic astronomy is ridicule of what does not conform to the sayings of the ancient sages.

A more tolerant view of Islamic astronomy is manifested by Kamalākara in the *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* that he completed in 1658, as by his brother Raṅganātha in his *Bhaṅgīvibhaṅgīkaraṇa*.⁴⁵ Kamalākara agrees with the Yavana opinion that the inhabited parts of the earth rise above the sphere of water so as, however slightly, to alter the local horizon, though he hastens to add that this opinion does not contradict the gods and ṛṣis.⁴⁶ Like Munīśvara he refers to Khāladātta, which he wrongly locates 22° West of Romaka; but he proceeds to give a set of the terrestrial coordinates – he calls longitude *tūla* (Arabic *tūl*) – of twenty cities.⁴⁷ The only cities on this list that are located outside of India are Kabul and Samarqand; and in the seven cases where cities are included in Ulugh Beg's geographical lists, the coordinates, with the exception of a few misreadings of *abjad* numbers, are identical.

Kamalākara confirms his acquaintance with Ulugh Beg by referring to the computation of a table of sines by "Mirjolukabega".⁴⁸ This knowledge probably reached him, however, through a more elaborate treatise than Ulugh

41. *Siddhāntasārvabhauma* 1, 38-39:1, 123:2, 253-254: and 2, 274-275.

42. *Siddhāntasārvabhauma* 2, 279.

43. CESS A5.

44. CESS A2, 115a.

45. *Bhaṅgīvibhaṅgīkaraṇa*, pp. 31-32.

46. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* 1, 120-126.

47. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* a, 172-174: Essay Table VIII 27.

48. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* 2, 89.

Beg's *Zj*, for that *zij* seems not to describe the eccentric-epicyclic planetary models with the protective spheres (*pāli*) of Ibn al-Haytham and the later Islamic astronomers though Kamalākara does;⁴⁹ Kamalākara, however, does not mention the equant.

Moreover, Kamalākara speaks with approval of the computation of planetary distances by the Yavanas on the basis of the interesting of the solid (*mārta*) spheres⁵⁰ – a computation that differs from the normal Indian procedure of making the distances of the planetary spheres inversely proportionate to the numbers of their rotations in a Kalpa.

It is not surprising, then, to find him quietly presenting as perfectly possible the Ptolemaic view of precession that Munīsvara had so heatedly attacked.⁵¹ Nor is it uncharacteristic that his fifth *adhikāra* is a treatise on geometric optics, a subject never before, to my knowledge, discussed in such detail in Sanskrit. I presume that here also he has utilized an Islamic source, though I have not as yet been able to identify it.

Kamalākara, then, was quite willing to prefer a Muslim opinion even though it is contrary to that of the *ṛsis*. But he neither accepted the methodology of Islamic astronomy, nor abandoned the basic procedures, models, and parameters of Indian astronomy. Two decades before he wrote, however, another Indian astronomer had gone much further in accommodating Islamic science.

Nityānanda⁵² was a Gauda Brāhmana connected with the court of Shāh Jahān at Delhi. In 1628 he completed an enormous *Siddhāntasindhu*, which he dedicated to Shāh Jahān's minister Āsaf Khān; no manuscripts of this work are available to me. In 1639 he composed a smaller work, entitled *Siddhāntarāja*, in twelve chapters. Of this I have examined a fragment in the Wellcome Institute Library in London (V. 36). This manuscript of 39 folios (numbered 1-36 and 38-40) contains the first two and a large part of the third chapters of the work.

In the *Siddhāntarāja* Nityānanda boasts that he will present absolutely new (that is, Islamic) material, whereas his predecessors have merely repeated each other⁵³ – not an unjustified criticism of Indian astronomers. But he feels it necessary to disarm his critics in the following verses,⁵⁴ which I translate thus:

49. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* 2, 255-284.

50. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* 2, 497-500.

51. *Siddhāntatattvaviveka* 2, 470.

52. CESS A3, 173a-174a, and A4.

53. *Siddhāntarāja* 1, 9.

54. *Siddhāntarāja* 1, 14-18.

“Having examined the *Romakasiddhānta* [i.e, a *zij al-Rūmī*], the *Saura*, and that of Brahmagupta, and knowing the (longitudes of the) planets corrected separately (by each), I have composed an accurate *siddhānta*”.

“It always attains in every way the equality between computation of the planets’ (positions) and observation that comes from the Romaka. In this (science, however,) they know that the *Sauratantra* is like a Veda, and that even that composed by Brahmagupta possesses suitable methods”.

“Then who was (this) Romaka who is numbered among the *munis*, the gods, and so on? I will tell you the answer to this (question); listen, as it was agreed to previously by Sūrya and Aruna”:

“because of (their) fondness for history and stories. Even Bhāskara was known as Romaka because of a curse pronounced by Indra: Yavana lived in Romaka’s city.”

“When the curse was removed because of the favor of these two, the sun himself in ancient times composed the best treatise here, which has the form of tradition (*śruti*) though in the guise of being Romaka’s”.

Nityānanda has based this myth, as he himself indicates, on one in the *Jñānabhāskara* or *Sūryārunasamvāda*⁵⁵ wherein Sūrya claims that he revealed the *Romaka (siddhānta)* to Romaka when he was born among the Yavanas because of a curse of Brahma, and that the *Romaka* was then revised by Romaka in Romakanagara. The author of the *Jñānabhāskara* was, I believe, thinking of the astrological *Romakasiddhānta* which claims to be part of a *Sriṣavāyanasamhitā*,⁵⁶ whereas Nityānanda refers to a work on Islamic astronomy. It is tempting, because of the name, to think of one of the works composed by Qāḍī Zādah al-Rūmī,⁵⁷ the teacher of and collaborator with Ulugh Beg perhaps his commentary on al-Jaghmīnī’s *Mulakkhaṣ fi al-hay’a*. Whatever the case may be, Nityānanda feels it necessary to justify Islamic astronomy to his audience not on the basis of a rational discussion of its methodology and an observational testing of its results (though he does state its superiority without adducing any evidence), but on the pretext of its being derived from the revelation of an Indian deity. Such a camouflage is certainly not new, as students of Abū Maʿshar’s *Kitāb al-ulūf*, for instance, well know;⁵⁸ but it is significant that even the most enlightened Indian astronomer of the seventeenth century did not dare to base his claims on the evidence of the senses.

55. A. Weber, *Verzeichnis der Sanskrit-Handschriften* (Berlin, 1853), p. 287.

56. CESS A5.

57. Storey, p. 67.

58. D. Pingree, *The Thousands of Abū Maʿshar* (London, 1968).

In fact, Nityānanda further feels constrained to cast his expression of the mean motion parameters of the planetary theories of his Muslim source in the traditional Indian form, and to give instructions for deriving from mean longitudes computed according to the Romaka those computed according to the Saurapakṣa and the Brāhmapakṣa, presumably to demonstrate that differences already exist within the Indian tradition, and that therefore the unfamiliarity of the Islamic parameters is not to be regarded as in itself vitiating them. Thus the normal Indian divisions of the Kalpa and other units of time are described;⁵⁹ the mean motions of the planets, their nodes, and the zodiac (*i.e.*, precession) are given as integer numbers of revolutions in a Kalpa;⁶⁰ and the computation of the *ahargana* follows the traditional pattern, though the epoch is noon at Lankā, which is (mean) sunrise at Romaka.⁶¹ The mean longitudes resulting from following these rules are then corrected by *bījas*, whose purpose seems to be to compensate for the inaccuracies involved in expressing the Islamic mean motions as integer rotations in a fixed time; Nityānanda states that they are necessary to bring the results into conformity with observations.⁶²

The dimensions of the Romaka's planetary models, however, are presented in Ptolemaic terms as eccentricities and radii of epicycles; and the circumferences of the *manda* and *śighra* epicycles of the Saura and Brāhma pakṣas are reduced by Nityānanda to the same terms.⁶³ The models themselves are thoroughly Islamic, with equants, protective spheres, and crank-mechanisms for the moon and Mercury.⁶⁴ The cosmology is almost equally Islamic;⁶⁵ the earth is surrounded by spheres of the Indian water, fire, wind, and space rather than the Aristotelian water, air, and fire, but beyond that come the seven planetary spheres in proper order. The eighth sphere, that of the zodiac, rotates at a precessional rate of 1° in 70 years; and the ninth sphere, crystalline and containing the constellations, rotates daily. Here there is no apology offered, nor indeed any justification of the presentation of these alien theories in Sanskrit.

Nityānanda's sine table, however, which gives the sine to five sexagesimal places for every degree from 1° to 90° with *R* equalling 60, is fully justified mathematically; for he gives complete rules for its computation, including Jāmsīd al-Kāshī's method (which was repeated by Qāḍī Zādh

59. *Siddhāntarāja* 2, 2-21.

60. *Siddhāntarāja* 2, 22-27.

61. *Siddhāntarāja* 2, 28-34.

62. *Siddhāntarāja* 2, 35-37.

63. *Siddhāntarāja* 3, 3-18.

64. *Siddhāntarāja* 3, 197 sqq.

65. *Siddhāntarāja* 3, 180-196.

66. WHMRL V. 36 ff. 18v-19.

al-Rūmī) of computing the sine of 1^0 and even of $1'$.⁶⁷

Unfortunately, the Wellcome Institute's manuscript breaks off in the midst of Nityānanda's descriptions of the Islamic planetary models so that I do not know the extent to which the rest of his work is indebted to Muslim astronomy. But a sufficient portion of the *Siddhāntarāja* has been investigated to show that his planetary system is completely Islamic, though some of its elements are reworked to fit into a traditional Indian mode of expression. But, despite some assertions (not uncommon in classical Sanskrit texts on astronomy) that the Romaka computations lead to results closer to observed positions than do the Sūryasiddhānta's or Brahmagupta's, Nityānanda shows no understanding of the role of observations in improving the models of celestial motions devised by astronomers or their parameters. He has, in fact, done nothing but to recast a Sanskrit translation of an Islamic astronomical work into a form more congenial, and perhaps more acceptable, to an orthodox *jyotiḥśāstrin*.

Indeed, we have already seen that such a Sanskrit translation of a work dependent on Ulugh Beg's *Zīj* was available in the seventeenth century, in Benares as well as in Delhi. And a manuscript of a Sanskrit *Jīva Ulugbegī* (*Zīj-i Ulugh Beg*) is preserved in the Mahārāja's Museum in Jayapur no. 45; it was acquired from Surata through Nandarāma Josī, who is probably the Nandarāma Miśra who wrote voluminously on astronomy and astrology at Kāmyakavana in Rājasthān between 1763 and 1778.⁶⁸ We do not yet know whether this translation is identical with that used by Munīsvara, Kamalākara, and Nityānanda. But that it was expected that translations of astronomical works would be made from Persian into Sanskrit (as they were under the Moghuls also from Sanskrit into Persian) is indicated by the existence of a special Persian-Sanskrit dictionary of astronomical terms intended to facilitate the process. This is the as yet unpublished *Pārasīprakāsa* composed under the patronage of Shāh Jahān in 1643 by Mālajit,⁶⁹ a scholar from Srīsthala in Gujarat who was awarded the title of *Vedāṅgarāya* by the Emperor for his efforts.

One such translation that illustrates again the influence of the Samarqand school on Indian astronomers is the *Hayatagrantha*.⁷⁰ This was edited a decade ago on the basis of three manuscripts in Benares, of which the oldest was copied by Nāgesa in 1765. The editor believed that it was composed in Benares in the eighteenth century; for it refers to Kāshī several times,⁷¹

67. *Siddhāntarāja* 3, 19-85.

68. CESS A3, 128b-130b.

69. CESS A4.

70. Ed. V. Bhaṭṭācārya as SBG 96, Vārānasī 1967.

71. *Hayatagrantha*, pp. 22, 95, 101-102, and 120-121.

and it computes the longitude of the sun's apogee "at the present time" for A. H. 1178, which began on 1 July 1764.⁷² These conclusions are rendered doubtful, however, by the fact that both the references to Kāshī and the computation of A. H. 1178 are omitted by Nāgeśa, and are therefore likely to be interpolations in the other two manuscripts. This doubt is strengthened to a certainty by the existence of a manuscript of the *Hayatagrantha* copied by Ṭikārāma Jyotiṣī in 1730 in the Mahārāja's Museum in Jayapura (no. 24), and the recording in 1875 of another in Oudh that was copied in 1694.

The *Hayatagrantha*, therefore, was probably written in the seventeenth century, but on the basis of a Persian work different from that available to Nityānanda in 1639. For the *Hayatagrantha's* parameters for its planetary models, which are completely Islamic, differ from those of Romaka as presented in the *Siddhāntarāja*. The *Hayatagrantha* refers by name to 'Ala' al-Dīn 'Alī al-Qūshjī (*allāma kauśajī nāma ulūkavegasya guruputra*) for his determination by "our observation" (*asmadrasada*) of the obliquity of the ecliptic,⁷³ and for the use of sunset epoch in Arabia (*arabadeśa*);⁷⁴ and it mentions "our observation" (*asmābhir vedhena rasadaḥ*) of the longitude of the solar apogee in Muḥarram 841 A. H., which is July 1437.⁷⁵ This suggests that the Persian original of the *Hayatagrantha* is the *Risālah dar hay'at* or *Fārsī hay'at* composed by al-Qūshjī⁷⁶ at Istanbul and dedicated to the Ottoman Sulṭān Muḥammad ibn Murād (1451-1481), the conqueror of Byzantium; the work was known in Mughal India as the commentary by Muṣliḥ al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Anṣārī and was dedicated to the Emperor Humāyūn (1530-1556). The arrangement of the two texts supports this hypothesis; each contains an introductory section in two parts, two main sections (divided into six and eleven *bābs* respectively in Persian, into four and ten in Sanskrit), and a supplement. I have not been able as yet to examine a copy of the Persian original in order to test this hypothesis. But the fact that the section on chronology in the *Hayatagrantha*⁷⁷ is a revision of that in Ulugh Beg's *Zij*⁷⁸ confirms the suggestion that the former represents a product of the school of Samarqand.

I do not wish now to go into the details of the *Hayatagrantha*. It should suffice to state that it consistently transliterates the Persian technical terms,

72. *Hayatagrantha*, p. 69.

73. *Hayatagrantha*, p. 24.

74. *Hayatagrantha*, p. 128.

75. *Hayatagrantha*, p. 69.

76. Storey, pp. 75-77.

77. *Hayatagrantha*, pp. 128-133.

78. L. P. E. A. Sédillot *Prologomènes des tables astronomiques d'Ouloug-beg* (Paris, 1853), pp. 7-28.

and then gives Sanskrit equivalents or explanations of them. In doing this the translator demonstrates his knowledge of the traditional Sanskrit terminology in geometry and in astronomy. From time to time either he, or more probably the person who computed the longitude of the solar apogee in 1765, adds Indian material; thus the *Sūryasiddhānta* is wrongly mentioned as using $22/7$ as a value of π ,⁷⁹ and the Indian measurements *aṅgula* and *yava* are added to the usual Persian *farsang*, *mīl*, and *gaz*.⁸⁰ But otherwise this is a straightforward translation of an introductory manual of astronomy through which a Sanskrit reader could learn the elements of late Islamic astronomy, but nothing about its methodology.

The most conscientious effort, however, to make Islamic astronomy and its methodology available in Sanskrit was that of Savāī Jayasiṃha of Jayapura in the early eighteenth century. Unfortunately, I have not yet had access to the unique manuscript, in the Mahārāja's Museum at Jayapura (no. 46), of Nayanasukhopādhyāya's translation of Naṣīr al-Dīn's *Tadhkira* with the commentary of al-Barjandī;⁸¹ it would indeed be fascinating to examine it and to discover in what form the "improvements" to the Ptolemaic planetary models devised in Marāgha were transmitted to eighteenth century India. But Jagannātha's translation of Naṣīr al-Dīn's version of the *Almagest*, the *Siddhāntasamrāṭ*, has been published, though not critically edited; from this it is apparent that Jagannātha also had access, presumably through the earlier Sanskrit translations used by Munīśvara, Kamalākara, and Nityānanda, to at least some of the views of Ulugh Beg and of his colleague, Jāmshīd al-Kāshī.⁸² For, after the thirteenth and last book of the *Almagest*, he adds a supplement which includes a *yantrādhyāya*, in which he describes the instruments that Jayasiṃha had set up in his observatories in imitation of those installed by Ulugh Beg at Samarqand,⁸³ and an explanation of Ulugh Beg's and al-Kāshī's derivations of sines.⁸⁴ And this is followed by a series of notes on how to deal with traditional aspects of Indian astronomy that are not directly touched on by Ptolemy or that are treated in a different manner by Ptolemy but not, in Jagannātha's opinion, fully enough. He even tacks on at the end a description of the *Sūryasiddhānta*'s planetary theory, presented in the traditional style.⁸⁵ The ambiguity towards scientific method implied by the inclusion of this material in Jagannātha's work is characteristic of Jayasiṃha's approach to astronomy.

79. *Hayatagrantha*, p. 16.

80. *Hayatagrantha*. p. 137.

81. CESS A4.

82. Storey, pp. 72-73.

83. *Siddhāntasamrāṭ*, vol. 2, pp. 1031-1048.

84. *Siddhāntasamrāṭ*, vol. 2, pp. 1048-1085.

85. *Siddhāntasamrāṭ*, vol. 2, pp. 1165 sqq.

For he did, with his Persian experts, construct those five famous observatories. Jagannātha mentions these observatories and some of the results obtained at them, and some obtained by other astronomers at other observatories.⁸⁶ From this passage and from the *Zij-i Muḥammad Shāhi* produced in the name of Jayasimha probably by Khayr Allāh Khān⁸⁷ we know that Jayasimha intended to follow the traditional method of Islamic astronomy in correcting astronomical parameters by careful observation, and that he hoped to improve the Islamic technique by simultaneously observing the same phenomena from five different localities. Though Jagannātha refers to some minor corrections to parameters like the obliquity of the ecliptic, it appears unlikely that the tables in the *Zij-i Muḥammad Shāhi* are very different from these in the *Zij* of Ulugh Beg; but no detailed study of Jayasimha's zīj has yet been made, so that we cannot decisively deny real significance to his work. However, the description of them given by Hunter in 1797⁸⁸ makes it clear that the structure of the tables is entirely Islamic. We do have for comparison, in Sanskrit, two works attributed to Jayasimha: a *Javavinodasārīnī* written in 1735, which contains tables for constructing the traditional Indian calendars, and a *Yantrarājaracanā*, a conventional Sanskrit treatise on the astrolabe. Neither work shows any trace of a new approach to astronomy. Moreover, other Sanskrit astronomical works written in Rājasthān and elsewhere in northern India in the eighteenth century seem *not* to have been influenced by Jayasimha. In fact, it seems probable that Khayr Allāh Khān was the sole designer of this ambitious project, though Jayasimha supported it enthusiastically and contributed to it financially if not to any great extent intellectually; the *Zij-i Muḥammad Shāhi* was never even translated into Sanskrit as had been the *Almagest*. And the translation of the *Almagest*, though extant in some two dozen complete or fragmentary copies, does not seem to have been used at all by those who composed treatises on astronomy in Sanskrit in the late eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.

Hunter, however, claims to have met at Ujjayinī the grandson of one of Jayasimha's assistants whom he believed to be capable of carrying on the tradition because, while trained in traditional Indian astronomy, he possessed manuscripts of the *Siddhāntasamrāṭī* and of a Sanskrit translation of Napier's logarithms, and he acknowledged the superiority of European science. To Hunter's regret, this paṇḍita soon died, "and with him the genius of Jayasimha became extinct".⁸⁹

86. *Siddhāntasamrāṭī*, vol. 2, pp. 1162-1165.

87. Storey, pp. 93-95.

88. W. Hunter, "Some Account of the Astronomical Labours of Jayasinha, Rajah of Ambere, or Jayanagar", *AR* 5 (1797), 177-211, esp. 205-209.

89. *Ibid.*, 210.

We may well doubt that much would ever have come from Hunter's friend. Even more dubious is Tod's famous epitaph of Jayasimha himself:⁹⁰ "Three of his wives and several concubines ascended his funeral pyre, on which science expired with him." The "science" he supported never had a chance to develop in Sanskrit because no Indians were ever trained to utilize the observatories or the translations in a constructive manner, and because, whatever the results of Jayasimha's own observations may have been, they were not published in Sanskrit.

We have seen, therefore, that though a few elements of Islamic astronomy were adapted by Indian astronomers before the Moghul period, they were not allowed to affect in any way the structure of the traditional science. Moreover, though efforts were made to introduce various of the works emanating from the School of Samarqand to Sanskrit-reading astronomers in the seventeenth century, the translations met with hostility on the part of some, indifference from most, and, at best, an attempt to Indianize them on the part of a few; but these translations and adaptations contained nothing that would instruct the Indians regarding the reason for the claimed superiority of Islamic astronomy, which was its methodology involving both a reliance on carefully planned and executed observations and a concern with the cinematics of the planetary models. Finally Jayasimha's activities, while they resulted in Sanskrit translations of the *Almagest* and a few other works that could have taught this methodology to the Indians, were apparently completely ineffective; his original works in Sanskrit were not innovative, the translations themselves were ambiguous, and the main contribution of his school to astronomy, the *Zij-i Muḥammad Shāhī* was addressed to a Persian rather than to a Sanskrit audience. Nityānanda, Kamalākara, Jayasimha and others may have recognized the superiority of Islamic over Indian astronomy, but they failed to find a way to persuade other Indian scientists of this fact, in part, I believe, because they did not themselves perceive wherein the superiority lay.

90. J. Tod. *Annals and Antiquities of Rajasthan* (repr. Oxford, 1920), vol. 3, p. 1356.